

were sown in rows at 20-cm spacing. Zero, 50, 100, or 150 kg N/ha; 0 or 13 kg P/ha; and 0 or 25 kg K/ha were applied. P and K were applied at planting. N was applied in equal splits 1 mo after sowing and at panicle initiation. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three

replications.

Weekly rainfall at Timbang Menggaris is shown in Table 1. Rainfall distribution was uneven and interrupted by drought. Yields were low because of low agronomic efficiency of applied fertilizer.

Significantly higher grain yields were

obtained with 100-13-0 kg NPK with burned rice husk and 150-13-25 kg NPK without burned rice husk (Table 2). With burned rice husk, high N and K did not increase the grain yield, but results suggest that 10 t burned rice husk/ha supplies 55-3-70 kg NPK/ha to rice. □

Effect of different nitrogen applications on rice grain yield

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We studied the effect of different N applications on IR6 yield at the Gomal

University Research Farm. Soil was a Zindani series of Entisols with 17% clay, 65% silt, 18% sand, 15.6% CaCO₃, 0.6% organic matter, pH 7.9, 4 ppm available P, 160 ppm K, and 3.5 ppm Zn. Twenty-seven kg P/ha as a single superphosphate (9% P) was applied basally, and different levels of N were incorporated in dry soil. Soil was flooded and the field was transplanted.

Results were highly significant. IR6 yielded highest (8.1 t/ha) with 138 kg N/ha as urea (see table). All fertilizer treatments increased yield significantly over the no-fertilizer treatment. Split-N-application plots yielded less than full application in dry soil, which produced highest straw yield, plant height, panicles/m², 1,000 grain weight, and net return/ha. □

Effect of different N applications on rice yield, Pakistan, 1982.

N (kg/ha)	Application method	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Increase (t/ha) over no-fertilizer		Net return ^b (US\$/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	1,000-grain wt (g)
		Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
Control	—	5.3 d	10.6 c	—	—	—	86.7	422	25.3
46	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	6.1 cd	11.8 bc	0.8	1.2	54.3	87.1	436	27.3
92	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	7.3 ab	14.3 ab	2.0	3.7	137.7	91.3	467	28.3
138	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	8.1 a	15.2 a	2.8	4.6	192.0	98.1	510	30.0
46	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	7.1 bc	13.6 ab	1.8	3.0	140.0	90.0	483	27.3
92	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	6.8 bc	14.7 a	1.5	4.1	94.8	92.1	486	27.7
138	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	6.8 bc	12.8 abc	1.5	2.2	78.0	87.4	486	28.0
92	Conventional (30+31+31)	7.0 bc	15.0 a	1.7	4.4	109.4	91.3	458	27.3

^a Means followed by similar letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Rice = \$86/t; urea fertilizer = US\$8.5/23 kg N.

Effect of bio, organic, and chemical fertilizers on rice grain yield

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We studied the effect of combined application of bio, organic, and chemical fertilizers on IR20 grain yield at TNRRI in Aug-Jan 1983. Soil was an alluvial clay loam with 137 ppm available N (alkaline permanganate method), 35 meq CEC/100 g, and pH 6.6.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Forty kg PK/ha was applied with 60 or 90 kg N as urea, farmyard manure (FYM) 0.609% N, green manure (Gm) 0.518% N fresh weight, and azolla 0.395% fresh weight. Fertilizers were incorporated 1 wk before transplanting.

N application increased grain yield significantly over the control (see table). At 60 kg N, urea alone performed better than in combination with organic manures. At 90 kg N, urea + azolla performed better than urea alone. At both N levels combinations with azolla performed best.

Effect of bio, organic, and inorganic fertilizers on grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	3.5
30 as urea + 30 as FYM	3.8
30 as urea + 30 as Gm	4.1
30 as urea + 30 as azolla	4.2
60 as urea	4.3
45 as urea + 45 as FYM	4.3
45 as urea + 45 as Gm	4.6
45 as urea + 45 as azolla	5.1
90 as urea	4.9
CD	0.4